

USL-5UEs-UGNSE 0.25, 0.5, 1.0 for the policy makers & shapers: the USL-5UE’s premises and their socio-economic and environmental snow ball effects for the governments and the United Nations (Draft 1)

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ABSTRACT

In this short paper, we explain the fundamental premises of USL and 5 UEs, how it operates, and its socio-economic and environmental implications over the next half a century and their initial funding strategies as the original USL is broken into USL 0.25, 0.5, and 1.0 sequentially each of which is designed to boost the regional or national average math skills by ½ year, 1 year, or 2 years respectively, which in turn will trigger the massive surplus economic growths. Using these massive growths, USL1 is trying to resolve the top 5 world global crises within a few decades. The various levels of collaborations, investments and donations are suggested at the end.

INTRODUCTION OF USL AND 5UEs

The Fundamental Premises of USL1 and USL

USL will use the colossal human capital potentials of STEM education (especially Math at the moment), because USL can make the learning 10-20 times faster and more effective usually, to trigger the equally colossal gains in the economy in exchange of the willingness of the governments - under a new UN-led treaty - to commit a reasonable ratios of the expected surplus gains in their economies to resolve the top 5 global crises. Each of the governments will mostly focus on resolving their crises, but they have to contribute to the world communities to prosper with the sustainable growths together not at the exclusion of half of the world that is poverty-stricken.

USL is the fastest, easiest, and cheapest way to redistribute the effectively gained, USL1.0-induced surplus economy (in a sustainable manner) to solve the top 5 most serious global crises (for all governments and the UN) based on the 5UE principles: to transition towards the resource-based, renewable energy-based, sustainable global environment and the circular economy, to help end the poverty much faster than without, while making the average people learn math and science faster and easier than prodigies. As the original USL is too fast and too disruptive (as it can literally make average people learn math and science 1,000%-50,000% times faster) to transform and people are too skeptical, we are currently focusing on only the 20% of its capacity called USL1 (USL 1.0) for the UN and the national governments.

USL Global Movements with Governments: 3 Steps of the Economic Gains

STEP 1) Math Education Reform USL 0.25 at the city and state government levels (advancing their regional average math skill levels by half a year, which normally takes 1-2-3 decades to most of the OECD countries, in just 1-2 years).

STEP 2) Math Education Reform USL 0.5 at the state government levels (advancing their regional average math skill levels by 1 year, which normally takes 3-5 decades to most of the OECD countries, in just a few years).

STEP 3) Math Education Reform USL 1 at the national government & the UN treaty levels (advancing their regional average math skill levels by 2 years, which (almost) never happened to virtually all of the OECD member countries, in just 2-5 years).

USL's Social Enterprise factor to benefit all

USL Global Movements with Governments: 3-Tiers of the Economic Gains driven by Social Enterprises

For each of the following step, we **will try to create local, regional, or national Social Enterprise for each government** - if they are willing as the gains are tremendous potentially - to share the profits together. So the governments will have the 3-layered benefits:

- 1) USL 0.x will enrich not only the math education that helps each USL x participating regions,
- 2) But also to prosper together as Social Enterprise board members of the corresponding regions.
- 3) Once the UN gets involved, then the certain portions of the massive surpluses to their local or regional economies will be distributed for the global social, energy, environmental, equality and poverty causes.

USL to Build the Social Enterprises Together With the Participating Governments

USL will be a Social Innovation (SI) and Social Enterprise (SE). We welcome for the USL pilot study-inviting governments to create Social Enterprises together for their states to boost not only their regional math education levels in less than 1 year what normally takes decades and thereby massively boosting their state economies.

We'll first try to start creating the USL+UGNSE1 (Unified Global Network of Social Enterprise 1) during the USL 0.25 or USL 0.5 pilot studies with the initially participating cities, states, and various countries, which will set the first stage to boost their average state or national math education to reach what normally takes a few decades with USL 0.25 (meaning boosting 1/4 Standard Deviations of the average math skills of the regions).

Based on the levels of collaborations, if satisfied then we will push to the USL 0.5 several decades or more (meaning boosting 1/2 Standard Deviations of the average math skills of the regions) USL 1.0 will be available exclusively to national governments that have completed the initial USL 0.25 and USL 0.5 first together.

Why These USL-5UE-URF Trio Schemes for Governments and the UN Will Work

As every government of a country should go through the sequence of USL 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2, 3, 4, 5+, etc., the governments have many reasons to adhere to the UN-led treaty and its protocols because there are huge economic gains or interests are at stake if they violate or deviate against. The more they deviate, the costs for the next USL versions for the country will be substantially larger later. So, a reason why we break up USL into these versions is to make sure that every government protects their environment maximally and transitions towards the Renewable Energy, etc., while overcoming their sovereign or public debts and eliminating poverties in their own countries as well as helping building the green infrastructures in the least developed parts of the world, etc., all at the same time. These are all possible due to the massive surplus economic gains after USL1.0 and beyond. The great economic gains at every level is used as the enticing schemes to all governments to maintain their integrity for the 5UEs as they will gain benefits locally via their sharings of the UGNSE1, but the long term benefits are even far greater than the gains from the SEs although they may need longer time to reap the harvests. It is such a win-win paradigm, we firmly believe that this idea should virally spread around the globe

USL 0.25, 0.5, and 1.0 and their implications

USL1 for the National Governments, NGOs and the UN

USL1 (with only less than the 20% of the full-capacity USL) can still do what is necessary: The most relevant UN groups and agencies (UNEP, UNIDO, UNDESA, UNDP, and UNESCO). Roughly speaking, the corresponding governmental departments or ministries will be those of Energy/Environment, of Commerce and Industry, of Infrastructures/Developments, and of Education/Culture. + will resolve not only the SE4All of the UN, but also 2-5 times faster than the current UN plans + will resolve the POST 2105 (the post-Millennium Development Goals) of the UN 5-10x faster than without USL1 (although still evolving) + will help building the sustainable communities much faster globally than otherwise possible. Moreover, there are back up plans.

USL's Global Social Implications

USL's primary objectives roughly consists of half socio-economical and the other half environment-energy-oriented:

- 1) to boost the global human capital using the revolutionary math/science education of USL, and then to help resolve most of the top 5 global causes within 20-25 years
- 2) to end the extreme poverty of the least developed countries
- 3) to reduce the gender/ethnic gaps in STEM and earnings drastically
- 4) to narrow the gaps between the rich and the poor countries
- 5) will give the opportunity for people to be independent because of the way it helps people to think structurally
- 6) will give the opportunity for people to unleash their artistic creativity with all the time freed up, satisfying Ken Robinson's 3 requirements for education [So, when our campaigns start in April 2014, please make positive noises if you want the real changes in our world!]
- 7) to drastically reduce the college student loan debt crisis, starting with that of the USA in 1-2 years (that is over 1.2 Trillion of dollars as a show case first) and similarly to other countries, ...
- 8) will attempt to create new generations of Renaissance men and women + will reduce the global income inequality for more than 5-10 times over the next half a century than without
- 9) All these happen while the users enjoy the extra free 5 years (of full-time job hours) of one's lives whether they are parents, students, or average adults who try to overcome your life-long traumas of math and science, or whether you are regular schoolers or home schoolers....

USL-5UE-URF Trio's Environmental Implications

The total costs to transition to at least 95% Renewable Energy worldwide will cost about 3-6% of GDPs over the next 30-50 years, which is about 7-10 times of the annual investments that most countries of the world are currently putting in. And the progress will be exceedingly slow. Instead with USL1-induced international treaty, this will be resolved breezily because the USL1-induced GDPs during this time will be extra surplus of the 8-12 times of the entire current world economic size.

- 1) To accelerate the progress towards the resource-based, sustainable communities, environments, and the circular economy which is otherwise difficult to be achieved very quickly...
- 2) to transition to the at least 95% renewable energy in 15-30 years, not longer
- 3) as such, carbon issues are automatically resolved and there will be no hassle after the first few decades
- 4) The current SE4All objectives of the UN can achieve their version 2, 3 goals with USL 1.0 alone.

- 5) The various other environmental crises such as the Amazon deforestations, plastics, the Fukushima radiation crises, etc., can be all resolved to the extents the economic infusions are necessary.

USL for the fundings

Why Philanthropists Should Support USL 0.25, 0.5, & 1

As USL1 will resolve all the top 5 crises within 20-25 years, we strongly urge philanthropists who would like to contribute to great causes should support us as soon as possible as we struggle to create various Social Enterprises for each state or country from the initial stage of USL 0.25 or USL 0.5.

Why Should Investors Get Involved For Projects of USL 0.X

USL series will consist of the double arms, mostly in the for-profit Social Enterprises at the national or regional levels or various Non-for-Profit entities. But its city or state level operations, while we struggle to establish as a firmly footed SEs, will need various financial infusions of the investors regardless and their ROIs will be still substantial.

Why Should the government officers should get involved for the pilot projects of USL 0.X

USL series will operate very transparently to make sure that each regional governments and their people benefit very much by sharing as early as the USL local operations of the USL 0.25 and USL 0.5. If USL operations boost the local education and economy transparently, there is no concern for the corruptions necessary. And the government officials are not required to participate in these sharings. They can simply group the properly qualified board members of the local USL 0.x operations to prosper together.

CONCLUSION

As each of the USL versions have the significant benefits to all the participating cities, states, and nations socially, economically, energy-wise, environmentally, and to drastically reduce the poor income distributions down the road, the people in the offices should share the intriguing proposals of the USL series, which will start with the USL 0.25 as it quickly boost the local math average skill sets by advancing them for 1/2 year (although normally this takes at least over 1 decade in developed countries): Furthermore, this can be accomplished within a few months, although the time will depend on the levels of the supports from the governments. We'll use

these USL 0.25 results as the stepping stones for the further collaborations to start a global movement to revolutionize the education, economy, energy, environment, and equality, all simultaneously, swiftly, and peaceful to thrive sustainably in every scale.

REFERENCES

For now, just check the evidences and data from www.uslgoglobal.com

We will add the references in the version 2 on.